

Tailoring quantum trajectories for strong-field imaging

A. SANCHEZ,^{1,†} V. A. TULSKY,^{2,†} K. AMINI,¹ B. D. BRUNER,³ G. ALON,³ M. KRÜGER,⁴ X. LIU,¹ T. STEINLE,¹ D. BAUER,² N. DUDOVICH,³ AND J. BIEGERT^{1,5,*}

¹ICFO-Institut de Ciències Fòniques, The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, 08860 Castelldefels (Barcelona), Spain

²Institute of Physics, University of Rostock, 18051 Rostock, Germany

³Department of Physics of Complex Systems, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot 7610001, Israel

⁴Department of Physics and Solid State Institute, Technion City, 3200003 Haifa, Israel

⁵ICREA-Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats, Barcelona, Spain

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work.

*jens.biegert@icfo.eu

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Strong-field imaging techniques such as laser-induced electron diffraction (LIED) provide unprecedented combined picometer spatial and attosecond temporal resolution by “self-imaging” a molecular target with its own rescattering electrons. Accessing the rich information contained in these experiments requires the ability to accurately manipulate the dynamics of these electrons—namely, their ionization amplitudes, and times of ionization and rescattering—with attosecond to femtosecond precision. The primary challenge is imposed by the multitude of quantum pathways of the photoelectron, reducing the effective measurement to a small range of energies and providing very limited spatial resolution. Here, we show how this ambiguity can be virtually eliminated by manipulating the rescattering pathways with a tailored laser field. Through combined experimental and theoretical approaches, a phase-controlled two-color laser waveform is shown to facilitate the selection of a specific quantum pathway, allowing a direct mapping between the electron’s final momentum and the rescattering time. Integrating attosecond control with Ångström-scale resolution could advance ultrafast imaging of field-induced quantum phenomena. © 2023 Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the Optica Open Access Publishing Agreement

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1. INTRODUCTION

The dynamics of electronic wavepackets is at the core of strong-field light–matter interactions [1]. Following ionization by a strong laser field, these wavepackets can subsequently undergo scattering or recombination with the target ion, encoding both structural and dynamical information of atomic and molecular systems. The mechanism of recombination with the target ion, which leads to emission of XUV or X-ray light, forms the basis of HHG spectroscopy in gaseous and solid state systems [2–4]. The rescattering process between the electron and the target ion, which imparts a momentum transfer onto the coherently scattered electron wavepacket, is the mechanism at the heart of laser-induced electron diffraction (LIED) [5–14]. In LIED, or any other rescattering-based imaging method, knowledge of the quantum trajectory of the electrons is crucial, and it is based on the unambiguous mapping of measured momentum to the time of rescattering [see Fig. 1(a)]. This mapping relies on the well-known strong-field approximation (SFA) [15,16]. In this model, the propagation phase acquired by the electron is determined by a quasi-classical action, which is a direct function of the electron’s canonical momentum \mathbf{p} and the laser vector potential \mathbf{A} (see Supplement 1). This gives rise to strong-field quantum trajectories that can be

classified into several branches, as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). One branch characterizes “direct electrons” that do not return to their parent target ion but move directly towards the detector. Another branch of trajectories describes electrons that rescatter after one or more returns to the ion [17–19]. In general, for a given final electron momentum and a given number of returns, there exist two sub-types of trajectories per laser cycle with different ionization and rescattering times, known “short” and “long.” Finally, the interference of all the quantum trajectories is mapped into the photoelectron momentum spectrum [19–24]. The application of LIED as a state-of-the-art imaging scheme requires either a single unambiguous electron trajectory or an effective method that can identify and disentangle the signals produced by multiple trajectories [25–28].

In this work, we perform a multidimensional strong-field ionization measurement [29]. We show that phase-controlled two-color laser fields shape the propagation of the quantum trajectories that are inherent in LIED measurements. These details are revealed via comparison of the experimental results with time-dependent Schrödinger equation (TDSE) simulations. Specific pathways, which are born within a narrow sub-cycle temporal window, are gated by the two-color field and are preferentially

Fig. 1. Trajectories in strong-field imaging experiments. (a) In techniques such as LIED, the target is ionized by a strong laser field and imaged by its own rescattered electrons. The measured rescattered momentum is the vector sum of the laser vector potential $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}_r)$ at the time of rescattering (black arrow) and the scattered momentum \mathbf{k}_r (green arrow) incurred upon interaction at the target. (b) The strong laser field (black), polarized along the \mathbf{e}_z axis, interacts with a target atom or molecule and generates photoelectrons whose trajectories are commonly classified as “direct” (green) and rescattered upon first (red), second (orange), or higher-order returns (not shown). The $3p$ atomic orbital of argon is used for illustrative purposes. (c) Schematic depiction of the experiment. A two-color, phase-controlled driving laser field, consisting of the laser fundamental laser pulse at central frequency ω and intensity I_ω (black curve), and its second harmonic at 2ω and intensity $I_{2\omega}$ (blue curve), is focused into a gas target. The momenta of the emitted electrons are detected. (d), (e) Trajectory filtering. By varying the relative phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ of a two-color mid-infrared (MIR) laser field, specific types of electron trajectories can be isolated. By varying $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$, by $\sim 0.6\pi$, one can switch between spectra that are dominated by odd returns at 1.7π (d) to those dominated by even returns at 1.1π (e). In (d) and (e), the combined laser field at the respective values of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ is shown, indicating the significant temporal reshaping of the total field as the relative two-color phase is varied.

selected in the rescattered photoelectron spectra. We thereby show that the dynamics of rescattered trajectories is controllable with sub-cycle time resolution. Such an approach has been successful in disentangling dynamical contributions to photoelectron spectra [30–33] as well as HHG spectra in atoms and molecules [2,34,35]. We additionally describe the effect of the laser wavelength—an important parameter that has not been fully explored due to the experimental challenges involved [12]. We demonstrate that for longer, mid-infrared (MIR) wavelengths, distinct quantum pathway contributions are distinguishable and fully separable by the correct choice of the relative two-color phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ between the fundamental ω and the second harmonic 2ω laser fields. The microscopic control over quantum trajectories removes the ambiguity in momentum-to-time mapping and provides unprecedented attosecond timing control and momentum imaging for techniques such as LIED.

2. EXPERIMENT

The near-infrared (NIR) experiments were carried out at a central wavelength of 788 nm using a 1 kHz Ti:sapphire amplifier with 30 fs (FWHM) pulses. The two-color driving field was produced using a type-I BBO nonlinear crystal to generate the second harmonic (394 nm). Both colors propagate collinearly through the remainder of the setup, thereby ensuring a high degree of phase stability between the two fields. A $\lambda/2$ waveplate for the fundamental wavelength is placed behind the nonlinear crystal so that the field

polarizations are mutually parallel. The group velocity walk-off between the pulses was compensated for using a birefringent crystal (calcite) and fused silica glass wedges. The relative two-color phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ is controlled by translation of the wedges. Subsequently, the beams are focused with a 37.5 cm focal length on-axis parabolic mirror into a pulsed gas jet (Parker-Hannifin) of Argon atoms. The emitted photoelectrons were detected in a velocity-map-imaging (VMI) spectrometer. The backing pressure and valve opening times were carefully controlled in gated mode in order to avoid substantial plasma defocusing.

For the MIR experiments, we used a home-built OPCPA that produces pulses with 3.2 μm central wavelength, 50 fs (FWHM) duration, and at a 160 kHz repetition rate [36]. Similar to the NIR experiment, the combined two-color driving field was produced and controlled using a AgGaSe₂ crystal, a $\lambda/2$ plate, and CaF₂ wedges. The fields were focused into a free flowing argon gas jet with a 5 cm focal length on-axis parabolic mirror, and the 3D momentum distribution was detected using a reaction microscope [37].

In both experiments, with reference to Fig. 1, the laser propagates along the \mathbf{e}_y axis, and its electric field is polarized along the \mathbf{e}_z axis. In the NIR measurements, the 2D photoelectron distribution in the VMI was detected with a multichannel plate detector in the $x - z$ plane. In both NIR and MIR experiments, we used similar laser intensities ($6 \cdot 10^{13}$ W/cm² and $5 \cdot 10^{13}$ W/cm² at central wavelengths of 3.2 μm and 788 nm, respectively) and second-harmonic conversion efficiencies (13% of the fundamental pulses). Finally, in order to account for the intensity fluctuations and the time integration recorded in each data set, we normalized the electron yields by fitting the rate of Ar⁺ ions with the Perelomov–Popov–Terent’ev (PPT) formula [38] in the tunneling limit (also known as the ADK formula; see, e.g., [39])

3. RESCATTERING IN THE MID-INFRARED AND NEAR-INFRARED REGIMES

First, we contrast the electron dynamics in the MIR regime with those for the frequently used NIR wavelengths. Figures 2(a) (MIR) and 2(b) (NIR) show the measured photoelectron kinetic energy release (KER) spectra along the polarization direction of the laser electric field as a function of the relative two-color phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. Figures 2(c) (MIR) and 2(d) (NIR) show the respective simulated spectra, produced by numerical solutions to the TDSE [40]. Varying the value of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ modulates the two fields’ interference and the resultant peak intensity. This leads to strong modulations of the photoelectron energy distribution with respect to the two-color phase, which is clearly observed in both the NIR and MIR regimes. At low energies, the cutoff energy of the direct electrons oscillates between values both $>2U_p$ and $<2U_p$, where $U_p = I_\omega/4\omega^2$ is the ponderomotive energy of the strong ω component in atomic units. Above the maximum cutoff energy of the direct electrons—at around $4U_p$ —there is a clear phase shift in the oscillating signals. Such a shift provides a clear fingerprint that a different family of trajectories—the rescattered electrons—is resolved.

The NIR measurements agree well with those observed in earlier studies [41]. In Fig. 2(b), the white and magenta dashed boxes delineate the branches formed in the high-energy (rescattering dominated) and low-energy (direct-electron dominated) regions of the spectrum, respectively. These branches overlap significantly

Fig. 2. Phase-dependent photoelectron yields in the MIR and NIR. (a), (b) Measured photoelectron kinetic energy release (KER) spectra along the laser polarization direction for MIR and NIR, respectively, as a function of the relative phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In (b), the white and magenta dashed boxes delineate the branches formed in the high-energy (rescattering dominated) and low-energy (direct-electron dominated) regions of the spectrum. (c), (d) Respective numerical calculations to the time-dependent Schrödinger equation (TDSE). The energy axes are scaled in units of the ponderomotive energy U_p of the strong ω component. Laser parameters: (a), (c) $\lambda = 3.2 \mu\text{m}$ at $I_\omega = 6 \cdot 10^{13} \text{W/cm}^2$ ($U_p = 57.3 \text{eV}$), Keldysh parameter $\gamma = \sqrt{I_p/2U_p} = 0.37$ for the ω field; (b), (d) $\lambda = 788 \text{nm}$ at $I_\omega = 5 \cdot 10^{13} \text{W/cm}^2$ ($U_p = 2.9 \text{eV}$), $\gamma = 1.65$, in all cases $I_{2\omega} = 0.13I_\omega$. In (a) and (c) the two high-energy rescattering branches in the spectra are resolved per one period of phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In (c), the cutoff energies predicted from semiclassical electron trajectories are plotted as colored lines: first- (red line) and second- (orange line), third- (yellow line) and fourth-return (green line). Solid lines identify regions where branches appear in the data; dashed lines show extrapolations of the cutoff behavior with respect to $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. Solid white line: predicted semiclassical cutoff for the direct electrons at low energies.

in energy, leading to the interference between their associated trajectories. These features are well reproduced by the TDSE simulations, as shown in Fig. 2(d). In this region, non-adiabatic tunneling plays a significant role [42]. In the deep tunneling regime, direct and scattered electrons (both forward-scattered and backward re-scattered) have very different amplitudes and their interference is weak. However, in the NIR, nonadiabatic effects modify their amplitudes, and their interference becomes stronger. Therefore, the distinction between direct and scattered electrons is less pronounced. In addition, for the NIR some re-collisions may take place under the Coulomb barrier, which further obscures the transition between the low- and high-energy branches. This imposes a significant challenge, preventing the identification and separation of the trajectory contributions in the NIR. While the second-harmonic field applies a sub-cycle control that modulates the different trajectories, their coherent contribution cannot be fully isolated at any phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$.

In the MIR, the measured photoelectron spectra are markedly different [Fig. 2(a)]. The key difference is evident in the region of rescattered electrons between $4 - 12 U_p$. Two separate branches for distinct ranges of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ are observed. In the first branch, the cutoff energy increases with increasing $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$, and reaches a maximum near $\sim 12U_p$ as $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ approaches a value near 0.5π . Above this value, there is a sharp jump into the second branch, which displays a lower cutoff energy and a different cutoff variance with respect to $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In the respective TDSE calculation [Fig. 2(c)], we plot the cutoff energies predicted for semiclassical electron direct and rescattered trajectories as dashed and colored lines. In the single-color case, odd- and even-numbered rescattered trajectories are known to produce differing cutoffs [43], and such effects also emerge in calculations using multi-color driving fields. We observe that the cutoff laws for rescattered electrons with odd-numbered returns correspond to the first branch, whereas even-numbered returns correspond to the second branch. These simulations clearly confirm the measured periodic dependence of the maximal MIR cutoff at $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} \simeq 0.5\pi, 2.5\pi, 4.5\pi, \dots$, due to the varying amplitude of the combined field with respect to the two-color phase. More importantly, the numerical analysis reveals the abrupt transition between the two types of trajectories, whose presence can be controlled by the choice of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In the following section, we expand upon the physical mechanism, induced by the laser field, that allows for identification and control over the observed trajectory type.

4. IDENTIFICATION OF ELECTRON TRAJECTORY TYPES WITH TIME-RESOLVED ENERGY SPECTRA

The TDSE calculations in Figs. 2(c) and 2(d) represent the total photoelectron distributions that accumulate over the full temporal duration of the laser pulse. However, the underlying dynamics that characterizes individual electron trajectories is hidden. A deeper insight can be obtained by unfolding the photoionization amplitude of the KER spectra in time. We calculate the time-resolved energy spectra by using the time-dependent surface flux approach [44,45] and a newly developed method to filter the photoionization amplitude [46] (see also Supplement 1). This method discriminates when electrons with a certain energy pass a sufficiently large spherical surface around the target. With this information one can calculate the times t_{sc} of the last scattering at the parent ion by propagating classical electrons backwards in time. This approach accounts for both direct and rescattered electrons in the presence of Coulomb effects and the laser field [47]. We are able to time-resolve the evolution of the photoelectron yield as a function of the key experimental parameters—the final electron kinetic energy and the relative two-color phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. This allows us to unambiguously connect the photoelectron yield, as calculated using the TDSE, with a specific class of classical trajectories. This circumvents the key shortcoming associated with other TDSE-based methods, by revealing the dynamics of individual trajectories that is otherwise obscured.

In Fig. 3 we consider two particular phase values, $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.1\pi$ and $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.7\pi$. For these values of the phase, the time-integrated photoelectron spectra have nearly equal high-energy cutoff [see Fig. 2(c)]. For both phases, temporal jumps in the accumulation of photoelectron yield for energies $\gtrsim 2U_p$ are found within well-defined ranges of t_{sc} . The photoelectron yield at the retrieved rescattering times during each half-cycle of the pulse are

Fig. 3. Simulated time-resolved formation of the photoelectron yield. (a) Electric field of the combined two-color pulse. Laser parameters for the fundamental and two-color fields: $\lambda = 3.2 \mu\text{m}$ at $I_\omega = 6 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ W/cm}^2$, and $I_{2\omega} = 0.13 I_\omega$, $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.7\pi$. The dark green arrows highlight the suppression (pointing down) and enhancement (pointing up) of the electric field strength within the laser cycle, relative to the single-color field. (b) Build-up of the photoelectron spectrum by electrons that scatter at time t_{sc} . The signal is collected for each optical cycle separately and thus is nullified when reaching the times indicated by dashed vertical lines. Solid colored lines: classically predicted time instants $t_{sc}(E_k)$ with colors indicating the number of returns. The data are dominated by the build-up of odd-order returns, whereas the even-order returns are suppressed. (c) Temporally integrated photoelectron yield, with contributions from each numbered return shown in their respective color. (d)–(f) Same data as in (a)–(c), but for the relative phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.1\pi$. Odd-order returns are then suppressed and even-order returns dominate the spectrum.

compared with the classically calculated rescattering times for each trajectory, indicated by the solid colored lines in Figs. 3(b) and 3(e). Strikingly, for $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.7\pi$, the rescattering times retrieved from the TDSE coincide with the classical first-return and subsequent odd-numbered return trajectories. In contrast, even-numbered returns are suppressed. The signal amplitude accumulated over the entire pulse [shown in Fig. 3(c)] is thus dominated by the odd returns. The data for $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.1\pi$ show completely complementary behavior, dominated by the even-numbered returns. In particular, we highlight the absence of signal at $t_{sc} = 3.5\pi$ in Fig. 3(e), indicating a near complete suppression of the first-return trajectory at its expected value of t_{sc} . We also note that the excellent agreement between quantum and classical results is indicative of the quasi-static (tunneling) regime under which the measurements and simulations are conducted.

This approach illustrates a key advantage of the two-color laser field. Spreading the data along an additional dimension (the $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ -axis) allows for the separation of even- and odd-order rescattering returns in a way that a single-color experiment could not. These concepts can be generalized to any value of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ on the odd- or even-order return branches (see Fig. 2). Any $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ from $\sim 1.3\pi$ to 2.1π will efficiently select for odd-order returns, whereas those from $\sim 0.5\pi$ to 1.3π will do so for even-order returns.

To understand the physical mechanism that underlies the control over the observed trajectories, we must examine the sub-cycle evolution of the two-color field [Figs. 3(a) and 3(d)]. Upon addition of the second-harmonic field, the ionization probability within each half cycle can be suppressed or enhanced relative to the single-color field. The sub-cycle dynamics of this process depends on the choice of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. For $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.7\pi$ [Figs. 3(a)–3(c)], inspection of the combined two-color driving field shows a suppression of the instantaneous field during the second (fundamental) half cycle and an enhancement during the first half cycle. This field configuration leads to the isolation of odd returns only. On the

other hand, for $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.1\pi$ [Figs. 3(d)–3(f)], the first half cycle is suppressed and the second is enhanced, resulting in even returns dominating the spectrum. Such fields thereby allow us to select the contribution of certain electron trajectories according to their ionization times.

In addition, we note that in Fig. 3(e), the cutoff energy for higher even returns increases from cycle to cycle, as expected because the semi-classical model predicts higher cutoffs with increasing number of returns [43]. For odd-order returns, the predicted cutoff decreases with increasing number of returns. Therefore, in Fig. 3(b), the highest cutoff is reached for the first return, and the yield remains identical above each new cutoff for subsequent returns. For certain energy intervals close to the highest cutoff, only very few electron trajectories contribute because of the decrease or increase of the cutoffs as a function of the number of returns.

The contributions of certain trajectories also depend on the long-range behavior of the potential. Figure 3 demonstrates that the long trajectories appear prominently in the data, indicated by their rescattering times. However, the short trajectories are nearly absent. This contrast between long and short trajectories is general to our experiment—it is observed for both even- and odd-numbered returns, and for all values of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In Supplement 1, we show that the first-return short trajectory contributes in the case of a zero-range potential, whereas for a long-range Coulomb potential, its contribution is suppressed. The long-range potential is also responsible for the prominent contributions of the higher-order returns, which occur due to significant Coulomb focusing of the electron wavepackets even for MIR driving fields [23,48]. This presents a well-known challenge for strong-field imaging techniques such as LIED due to the presence of multiple trajectories. Strategies for further reducing the number of contributing trajectories are considered in the next section.

5. ISOLATING INDIVIDUAL TRAJECTORIES FOR STRONG-FIELD IMAGING

The ability to manipulate the underlying dynamics with sub-cycle resolution allows us to overcome a primary challenge in LIED— isolating the contribution of a single class of trajectories. Such isolation can remove unwanted interferences in the spectra and allow for an unambiguous mapping between energy and rescattering time of the electrons. Importantly, the ability to isolate a single trajectory enables extraction of LIED data without the need for advanced retrieval algorithms to extract the signals of interest.

Any trajectory can be visualized by examining its rescattering window using the semiclassical model. By varying the second-harmonic intensity, one can continuously modulate the electrons' ionization and rescattering time windows. Figure 4(a) depicts the energy range associated with a single first-return trajectory contribution, and illustrates its mapping to rescattering times. In this calculation, the relative phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ between the fields is set to 1.35π . This value is chosen based on the results of Fig. 5. It represents the relative phase that provides the highest degree of discrimination between long and short trajectories, given by the ratio between their yields at their respective rescattering times. As the intensity ratio $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega}$ is increased, while keeping I_{ω} constant, we enhance the acceleration of the rescattering electrons. This enables control of the rescattering time window, which can be shifted with sub-femtoseconds resolution. As $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega}$ approaches unity for a $3.2\ \mu\text{m}$ fundamental field, such control enables shifting of the rescattering window over a 3 fs range, representing one-third of an optical period. Similar shifts occur for the third-return trajectory, at larger values of t_r .

The two-color field also allows for control over the rescattering energy. It is well understood that the first and third returns share similar rescattering solutions while being delayed by one optical cycle, leading to a small difference in their cutoff momenta or energies [33]. In this example, the third return covers a narrower range of electron energies with a lower cutoff energy. We can therefore construct a single-trajectory window for which only the first rescattering return contributes. The temporal and energy ranges of the single-trajectory window can be highlighted by the shaded areas in Fig. 4(a). The two-color field enables us to accurately tune their energy difference, thereby providing the key mechanism for isolating a single-trajectory contribution.

In Fig. 4(b), we re-interpret these results with respect to the trajectories' scattered momentum, and directly connect the predicted rescattering times to the observables in strong-field imaging. We define a longitudinal momentum width, ΔP_{\parallel} , equal to the difference between the cutoff momenta of the first- and third-return trajectories, as obtained through semiclassical calculations. Accordingly, because the first-return trajectories reach higher rescattered momentum than the higher odd-order returns, ΔP_{\parallel} represents the spectral window associated with a single-trajectory contribution. For a single-color field, ΔP_{\parallel} is a constant, indicated by the black dashed line. However, the two-color field can dramatically tune the separation of the first- and third-return trajectories in momentum space. At $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} \sim 1.35\pi$, the single-trajectory window, ΔP_{\parallel} , is 1.5 times larger compared with the single-color case. As we increase the intensity ratio further, to $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega} = 1$, the single-trajectory window expands dramatically, becoming three times larger compared with the single-color case. Additional calculations for the limiting case of $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega} = 1.00$ confirms that this control scheme can be generalized for a large range of two-color

Fig. 4. Selection of a single LIED trajectory using strong MIR fields. (a) Mapping the rescattering times t_r and rescattered photoelectron kinetic energies for the first- and third-return trajectories. The laser parameters of the fundamental laser field are $\lambda = 3.2\ \mu\text{m}$ at $I_{\omega} = 6 \cdot 10^{13}\ \text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, and the relative intensities of the fundamental and second-harmonic are given by $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega} = 0.13$ (beige line) and $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega} = 1.00$ (gray line). In both cases, the relative two-color phase is $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.35\pi$. The time-energy ranges that produce a single return trajectory are shown by the shaded areas, enclosed by dashed lines. Such control by the two-color field enables shifting of the temporal rescattering window over a 3 fs range, representing one-third of an optical period, whereas the differences in cutoff energies between first and higher-order returns extend over $\sim 3U_p$. (b) Single LIED trajectories in momentum space. ΔP_{\parallel} , defined as the difference between the first- and the third-return maximal momentum (in atomic units), represents the rescattered momentum window associated with a single, first-return trajectory contribution only. Using semiclassical calculations, ΔP_{\parallel} is plotted as a function of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. The maximum ΔP_{\parallel} (at $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} = 1.35\pi$, as indicated by the red star) at a two-color intensity ratio of $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega} = 0.13$ (beige line) is 1.5 times greater compared with a single-color field (black dashed line). For a larger intensity ratio $I_{2\omega}/I_{\omega} = 1.00$ (gray line), the maximum ΔP_{\parallel} is three times larger (indicated by the blue star) than for the single-color field.

field parameters (see Supplement 1 Fig. S3). Therefore, a straightforward manipulation of the relative intensity and phases of the two-color field can serve as an accurate control knob to manipulate the contributing trajectories in strong-field imaging experiments, and can provide a single-trajectory contribution over a large range of momenta.

6. CONTROL OF LONG AND SHORT ELECTRON TRAJECTORIES

In addition to the isolation of single, first-return rescattering trajectories as described in the previous section, we now show that the sub-cycle manipulation of the laser field provides control over the roles of the short- and long-trajectory branches. In general, both branches play a role in strong-field laser–matter interactions [49]. In HHG, it is well known that contributions of the long and short branches are controllable via phase matching [50]. In strong-field imaging, each odd or even return also contains a short- and a long-trajectory branch, which have different rescattering times and rescattered momenta. However, LIED relies on single, isolated scattering events and an unambiguous mapping between the rescattering time and energy [51]. In such cases, how can one discriminate between long- and short-trajectory branches, and control their relative contributions in the photoelectron spectra?

Addressing this question requires sub-cycle temporal resolution, provided by the two-color driving field. Again, the key properties of the control scheme rely on the relative phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In Fig. 5(a), we consider the calculated TDSE yield at a specific energy, namely, the third-return cutoff at each corresponding value

Fig. 5. Control of long and short first-return electron trajectories. Calculated, time-resolved TDSE yield (blue shaded areas) for the cutoff energy of the third rescattering return. The yields at the cutoff energies [corresponding to the yellow solid line in Fig. 2(c)] are extracted from the simulation in Fig. 3, and are plotted as a function of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ and the rescattering time t_r . At this cutoff energy, first-return electrons are expected to dominate the signal. The laser parameters of the fundamental laser field are $\lambda = 3.2 \mu\text{m}$ at $I_\omega = 6 \cdot 10^{13} \text{W/cm}^2$, and the relative two-color intensities are $I_{2\omega}/I_\omega = 0.13$. Red lines: expected semiclassical rescattering times for the first-return long and short trajectories. The long trajectory rescattering times are concurrent with a large increase in the yield, whereas the short trajectory rescattering times are not. The relative phases $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} \sim 0.35\pi$ (red triangle) and 1.35π (red star) give the highest discrimination of first-return long trajectories over first-return short, given by the ratio between their yields at their respective rescattering times. The TDSE data are averaged over an energy interval $\pm 0.25U_p$. Right panel: calculated, time-resolved TDSE yield for a single-color field, shown as a function of t_r . The accumulation of the photoelectron yield here is consistent with both long and short trajectories, providing a far lower degree of discrimination between the two trajectory types.

of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. These energies are shown by the yellow line in Fig. 2(c). For these values, first-return electrons are expected to dominate the signal. We can therefore track the accumulation of the first-return yield with respect to both $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ and the rescattering times t_r . In this representation, one can visualize the rescattering times at which the yield begins to accumulate, and compare them with the expected semiclassical rescattering times for the first-return long and short trajectories (marked by the red lines).

The left panel of Fig. 5 shows that by varying $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$, one can manipulate the relative yield of the long and short first-return trajectories. It can be clearly observed that the long-trajectory scattering times are consistent with a large increase in the yield for all values of $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$. In contrast, the rescattering times of the first-return short trajectories are inconsistent with the accumulation of the yield, and thus, the first-return long trajectories dominate the underlying mechanism. This finding is fully consistent with Figs. 3(b) and 3(e), where the time-resolved formation of the photoelectron yield starts building up only after the rescattering times for the first-return short trajectories. We also note that there is no appreciable yield for the first return for $0.5\pi < \phi_{\omega/2\omega} < 1.3\pi$, since these phases correspond to the branch of even-order rescattered trajectories as shown in Fig. 2(c). In the right panel of Fig. 5, we plot the same calculated TDSE yield as a function of t_r but for a single-color field. Here the accumulation of the photoelectron yield is consistent with both long and short trajectories. Although the Coulomb field contributes to their selection (see Supplement 1 Fig. S2), Fig. 5 shows that a near complete discrimination between long and short trajectories is unique to strong field dynamics

driven by the two-color field, and is controllable via an appropriate choice of the relative two-color phase. The highest degree of discrimination, given by the ratio between the yields of the long and short trajectories at their respective scattering times, occurs for $\phi_{\omega/2\omega} \sim 0.35\pi$ and 1.35π .

Thus, our analysis reveals that the two control parameters of the process, namely, the relative intensities and phases of the two colors, perform complementary actions in filtering the number of active trajectories. The phase $\phi_{\omega/2\omega}$ enhances the contribution of the long trajectory relative to the short, while altering the intensity ratio enhances the contribution of the first rescattering trajectory relative to the higher returns. Therefore, we can reduce the dynamics of the interaction to that of a single class of trajectories by appropriate tailoring of the driving laser field.

7. CONCLUSION

Our work demonstrates an important advance in using quantum control in strong-field imaging techniques such as LIED. We conclusively show the ability to isolate the contribution of a single quantum trajectory over an enhanced spectral range. This opens up exciting new prospects for LIED imaging with attosecond temporal resolution. By tailoring the sub-cycle structure of the electric field, one can select for distinct branches of odd- or even-return rescattering electrons, filter a single-return relative to a multiple-return electron, and maximize the contribution of long trajectories over short trajectories. This control scheme removes ambiguities in timing despite the multi-cycle nature of the driving laser field, and allows for a large momentum range for imaging. We have shown that MIR driving lasers are crucial for realizing such concepts, by allowing a direct sub-cycle control of electron trajectories that cannot be applied with NIR laser fields. Beyond LIED, our findings have significant implications in other areas of strong field physics, including the dynamics of non-sequential double ionization [52–54], and various imaging and spectroscopic applications [7,22] with additional optical gating techniques [55]. Our approach can also be applied in a large variety of strong-field photoelectron spectroscopy schemes. The ability to select a single ionizing quantum trajectory has important implications for studies of Dyson orbital imaging [56,57], molecular chirality [58], and charge migration in more complex systems [59]. Such control over re-collision trajectories provides further enticing prospects to control and shape attosecond-duration electron wavepackets and photon pulses in space [60] and time.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

Supplemental document. See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

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